

Safe Organisation and User Registry for Sensitive Data (SOURSD) Technical Specification

Minimum dataset and configurable rules

Version 0.4

Document Control

Authorised version document control			
Version:	February 2025 – Version 0.4		
Document manager:	Rachel Tesfaye, Senior Technical Programme Manager, HDR UK		
Authorised by:	Various – HDR UK		
Classification:	Public	If restricted - Defined group:	NA
Retention:	In perpetuity (unless superseded by subsequent version)		
Master copy location:			

Record of changes			
Version:	Date	Section name/ number:	Changes made:
V 0.1	December 2024	All	Standard separated into this technical specification document and a guidance document for Data Custodians providing guidelines around Safe Organisation and User Checks. Updates to data fields included in minimum dataset table within this technical specification. Update of configurable rules for Data Custodians.
V 0.2	January 2025	Minimum dataset	Addition Data Use Register variables - Safe Projects, Safe Outputs, Safe Settings, Safe Data.
V 0.3	February 2025	All	Implement changes following internal HDR UK review of technical specification.

Contents

Executive Summary 4

Minimum dataset: mandatory and optional fields 6

Configurable rules for Data Custodians

DRAFT

Executive Summary

Aims

The Safe Organisation and User Registry for Sensitive Data (SOURSD) 'Know Your User and Organisation' technical solution is an open-source web-based tool. SOURSD is designed to automate existing processes and streamline the decision-making processes for Data Custodians to assess the "Safe People" criteria of the [Five Safes Framework](#) when assessing projects. SOURSD does not make decisions as to who is a "Safe Person" or a "Safe Organisation" but provides profile information associated with a User and their relevant associated Organisation and whether that profile breaks any Data Custodian ([Trusted Research Environment](#) (TRE)/NHS Research Secure Data Environment (SDE)/Safe Haven) customisable rules.

This technical specification aims to:

- Define a **minimum dataset** including mandatory and optional data fields to enable TREs/SDEs to verify Users and Organisations as "safe", in line with the [Five Safes Framework](#) Safe People principle. The minimum dataset will be populated by Users, Organisations and Data Custodians within the SOURSD tool.
- Define a reference list of **rules** which TREs/SDEs can choose to configure (or not) within the SOURSD tool to flag potential issues with the "safeness" of a User or Organisation. Decision models will be based on existing TRE/SDE policies and procedures related to User and Organisation data access.

Scope

This technical specification applies specifically to **mandatory and optional data fields** which should be populated by Users and Organisations within the SOURSD tool, to support Data Custodians to apply agreed rules. For clarification, if a field is marked as "mandatory" it does not mean that it is mandatory that a User or Organisation populate the field in a specific way, only that it is mandatory that the field *is* populated. It is the rules engine which assesses *how* a mandatory field is populated e.g.

it may be mandatory to capture if a User has undertaken mandatory TRE/SDE specific local training prior to accessing a TRE/SDE. The rules engine for particular TREs/SDEs may then flag Users who have not completed specific mandatory TRE/SDE local training.

This specification is based on agreed minimum requirements for a User and Organisation verification common model (illustrated below). This common model includes minimum data fields that will be populated by Users and Organisations within SOURSD, alongside Project-level data that will be provided by Data Custodians.

*Keycards: Access granted to a TRE/SDE including date granted and date of expiry. *Inclusion in public record and signed declaration: [UKSA Digital Economy Act Research Code of Practice and Accreditation Criteria](#)

Organisations can confirm if a User is 'affiliated' with them and has appropriate expertise to work on sensitive data projects. The Senior Responsible Officer (SRO) within the organisation is responsible for setting up the Organisation's SOURSD account and nominating administrative Delegates.

SOURSD provides the capability for Users and Organisations across different sectors to provide information once, within a single tool, avoiding duplication of effort when seeking access to data within a TRE/SDE for legitimate research purposes. Data Custodians can view the Project Registry within SOURSD, and they can associate current and historical Projects with Users and Organisations.

Organisations and Users can also view projects with which they are associated, and Organisations can see which Users from their Organisation are working on which projects.

SOURSD can capture Project Approvals and User / Organisation validations based on information provided by Data Custodians. As an **optional** feature for Data Custodians, after a User and Organisation has been approved to work on a specific project, a Data Custodian can choose to set up an account with appropriate permissions for the User to log into their TRE/SDE and analyse data.

Minimum Dataset

The minimum dataset table below details the **mandatory and optional fields** that will be populated by Users, Organisations, and Data Custodians within the SOURSD tool. This table also details fields that will be auto populated by SOURSD, through automated data feeds from existing systems.

Terminology

- **“Data Custodian”**: This is the entity equivalent to the “Host Organisation” (as defined in the standard [Data Access Agreement \(DAA\)](#) and the [Safe People Guidance](#)). This entity hosts and controls a TRE/ SDE / Safe Haven, or a team providing access to a research dataset. Data Custodians nominate administrator(s) to populate Data Custodian-specific information within SOURSD, and decisions based on information provided by “Users” and “Organisations”. Data Custodians can choose which of the SOURSD capabilities they wish to adopt at a granular level, e.g. simply looking up User/Organisation profiles to assess their “safeness”, or adopting an end-to-end solution recording User/Organisation verifications, recording project approvals, and supporting Single Sign-On (SSO) of Users into secure environments to access project specific data.
- **“User”**: This is the entity equivalent to the “Approved Researcher” (as defined in the standard [DAA](#) and the [Safe People Guidance](#)). A User accesses and uses the data in a TRE/SDE/Safe Haven for Approved Project(s). A User is an individual who is an employee, student, or has an honorary contract with an Organisation. A User populates their SOURSD profile with information to verify their identity, affiliations, research experience, training and accreditations, and can request that their Organisation(s) “affiliate” them. User’s SOURSD account is associated with an individual through a unique identifier and can move with them regardless of employment changes.
- **“Organisation”**: This is the entity equivalent to the “User Organisation” (as defined in the standard [DAA](#) and the [Safe People Guidance](#)). A university, commercial research organisation, administrative body or other organisation which is responsible for individuals (Users) using a Data Custodian

TRE/SDE/Safe Haven service. An Organisation could also be a research sponsor. The Organisation populates their SOURSD profile with information to verify their organisations' identity, confirms a Senior Responsible Owner (SRO), nominates administrative Delegates, and affiliates their Users. Organisations can invite Users to either create a new SOURSD account or associate an existing SOURSD account with the Organisation. Users can request that Organisations affiliate them.

- **“User/Organisation Validation”:** Data Custodians assess User and Organisation profiles within SOURSD and make decisions to validate the User or Organisation to work on a specific project. This is based upon whether a User/Organisation is considered “Safe”, following the [Five Safes Framework](#). Validating a User or Organisation within a Project is distinct from Project Approval e.g. a User could be considered “safe” and be validated to work on a Project, but the Project is then not approved for other reasons. Validation can be completed for Users/Organisations who are working on projects which are either in the pre-approval or approved state.
- **“User Affiliation”:** Following a request from a User via SOURSD, Organisations are responsible for reviewing a User’s profile and confirming that the User is “affiliated” with the Organisation. By confirming affiliation, the nominated administrative Delegate from Organisation is confirming that: 1) there is an acknowledged link such a contract of employment, honorary contract or student enrolment between a User and the Organisation 2) The SOURSD User profile matches that of the Organisation employee / student. 3) The Organisation approves this employee / student to access sensitive data. 4) The organisational email address of the user corresponds to the correct email address in your Organisation. If a particular employer or university is not known by SOURSD, then a User can ask their Organisation to register a new SOURSD account. Affiliation only has to be completed once for each User-Organisation relationship, i.e. affiliation is not on a per project basis. However, Organisations can see all the projects a User is validated to work on, and if necessary, request that a User is either added or removed from a project.

- **“Project”**: A project set up within SOURSD by a Data Custodian. The properties of a Project align with the [Data Use Registry](#) standard. Users and Organisations can be added to or removed from projects by Data Custodians either preapproval or post approval.
- **“Project Approval”**: This is the entity equivalent to the “Project Approval” and/ or “Approved Purposes” (as defined in the standard [DAA](#)). A project is approved by a Data Custodian.

Organisation Senior Responsible Officer and Delegate Information

ID	Data field description	Why is this field captured?	Mandatory / Optional field	Populated by (owner)	Format field is populated	How field is populated
1.1	Senior Responsible Officer (SRO) full name	Organisations are responsible for the behaviour of a User, who is either their employee, on an honorary contract, or a student of their institution. Organisation Senior Responsible Officers are responsible for:	Mandatory	Organisation Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)	Free text field	Fields 1.1-1.5 should be populated by Senior Responsible Officer (SRO) within an Organisation. An SRO should have suitable authority and seniority to delegate responsibility to
1.2	Senior Responsible Officer (SRO) department		Mandatory	Organisation Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)	Free text field	

1.3	Senior Responsible Officer (SRO) email address	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating a SOURSD account • Nominating administrative Delegates from the organisation to affiliate Users employed by/enrolled with the Organisation. • Providing information within an Organisation's SOURSD profile 	Mandatory	Organisation Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)	Free text field	administrative Delegates within the Organisation.
1.4	Senior Responsible Officer (SRO) position/job title		Mandatory	Organisation Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)	Free text field	The SRO email should be populated with the relevant team/department mailbox account. Multiple individuals within the same team/department will have access to the Organisation's SOURSD account through administrator permissions.
1.5	Terms and Conditions	The Senior Responsible Officer (SRO) confirms they understand conditions and guidelines for using the SOURSD tool including: acceptable behaviour, disclaimers, limitations of liability, termination provisions, applicable law and provisions.	Mandatory	Organisation Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)	Checkbox	

1.6	Delegate department	Delegates are nominated administrative groups or individuals within an Organisation that affiliate Users Delegates are responsible for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Affiliating Users based upon the 4 criteria listed under the “User Affiliation” definition above. Accepting the SOURSD terms of use 	Mandatory	Organisation Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)	Dropdown options: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> HR department IG department Contracts department Legal department Other 	Delegates should be of sufficient seniority and relevant responsibility. Examples of Organisation Delegates include contact for Project proposals and contracts and could include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> HR representative DPO representative Contracts representative Legal representative
1.7	Delegate name		Mandatory	Organisation Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)	Free text field	
1.8	Delegate email address		Mandatory	Organisation Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)	Free text field	

1.9	Delegate job title		Mandatory	Organisation Senior Responsible Officer (SRO)	Free text field	
Organisation Profile Information						
ID	Data field description	Why is this field captured?	Mandatory / Optional field	Populated by (owner)	Format field is populated	How field is populated
1.10	Organisation name	Provide information to Data Custodians on official legal Organisation name that can be verified through a through a 'Know Your Organisation' check e.g. Companies House filing verification.	Mandatory	Organisation /Organisation Delegate	Free text field	This field should be populated with the Organisation name to verify the details provided match those listed on Companies House or other regulatory sources.
1.11	Organisation address	Provide information to Data Custodians on the registered headquarters / location of the Organisation that can be	Mandatory	Organisation /Organisation Delegate	Free text field with address auto population	This field should be populated with the Organisation address to verify the details provided

		verified through a through a 'Know Your Organisation' check e.g. Companies House filing verification.				<p>match those listed on Companies House or other regulatory sources.</p> <p>If your headquarters is based outside of the UK, please add the international address of your registered headquarters manually below and, if relevant, add the UK address of your UK subsidiary within the UK subsidiaries section.</p> <p>Address fields (address lines, country, county, postcode) will auto populate based on an initial input of free text.</p>
1.12	Organisation sector	Provide information to Data Custodians on the sector the Organisation is associated with.	Mandatory	Organisation /Organisation Delegate	<p>Dropdown options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Healthcare Providers 	This field should be populated with the Organisation sector aligned with Standard Industry Classification (SIC) codes as

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pharmaceutical and Biotechnology Companies (non-SME) • Pharmaceutical and Biotechnology Companies (SME) • Academic Research Institutions • Government Agencies: e.g., DHSC, Regulatory bodies, NICE • Non-Profit Organisations (e.g., foundations, advocacy groups, charities) • Other for-profit organisations (non-SME) 	<p>listed in Companies House or other regulatory sources.</p>
--	--	--	--	--	--	---

					<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Other for-profit organisations (SME) 	
1.13	Business registration identifier – Companies House filing	Provide a ‘Know Your Organisation’ check for Data Custodians, verifying an Organisation’s Companies House filing, where applicable.	Optional	Organisation Delegate	Free text field to populate Companies House ID	Where a Companies House filing exists for an Organisation, this field should be populated with the Company number/ID as listed in Companies House.
1.14	<p>For each charity registration</p> <p>Charity registration country and ID</p>	Provide a ‘Know Your Organisation’ check for Data Custodians, verifying a Organisation’s charity registration information, where applicable.	Optional	Organisation Delegate	<p>Dropdown options for registered UK country:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> England Wales Scotland Northern Ireland England and Wales <p>Free text field for charity ID</p>	<p>Where a charity registration identifier exists for an Organisation, this field should be populated with the charity registration information e.g.:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The Charity Commission The Scottish Charity Regulator (OSCR) The Charity Commission for Northern Ireland

1.15	Research organisation identifier	Provide Data Custodians with a recognised persistent identifier associated with any research organisation.	Optional	Organisation Delegate	Free text field	Where a Research Organisation Registry (ROR ID) identifier exists, this field should be populated with the ROR ID e.g. https://ror.org/01abcde11
1.16	Organisation size	Provide Data Custodians with Organisation company size information, e.g. small-to-medium sized business, large enterprise.	Mandatory	Organisation Delegate	Dropdown options: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small enterprise • Medium-sized enterprise • Large enterprise 	This field should be populated with the Organisation size based on the number of employees: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Small enterprise: 1 to 49 employees • Medium-sized enterprise: 50 to 249 employees • Large enterprise: 250 or more employees

1.17	Organisation website	Provide the URL for the Organisation website	Optional	Organisation Delegate	Free text field	This field should be populated with the main landing page of the Organisation website.
1.18	For each UK subsidiary Subsidiary name	If the Organisation is based outside of the UK, provide information to Data Custodians on registered location(s) of sites / subsidiaries within the UK	If creating subsidiary, Mandatory, otherwise Optional	Organisation Delegate	Free text field	Where an Organisation's headquarters are based outside of the UK, this field should be populated with all UK subsidiary names, as listed in Companies House or other regulatory sources.
1.19	For each UK subsidiary Subsidiary address		If creating subsidiary, Mandatory, otherwise Optional	Organisation Delegate	Free text field with address auto population	This field should be populated with the UK subsidiary address as listed in Companies House or other regulatory sources. Address field (address lines, country, county, postcode) will auto populate based on an initial input of free text.

1.20	Data security compliance	Provide Data Custodians with confidence that a Organisation is compliant with required data security certifications, to align with existing TRE/SDE policies and procedures.	Optional	Organisation Delegate	<p>Free text field to provide certification ID.</p> <p>Date selection field to confirm expiry date of certification</p> <p>Document upload field to provide up to date certification document</p>	To populate this field, the Organisation will select one or more data security compliance accreditations and provide an accreditation ID. Accreditations include: Cyber Essentials, Cyber Essentials+, ISO27001, DSPT (select one or more).

User Profile: Identity Information

ID	Data field description	Why is this field captured?	Mandatory / Optional field	Populated by (owner)	Format field is populated	How field is populated
2.1	Full name	Provide a User's official registered legal name that can be matched with employee or student records.	Mandatory	User	Free text field	This field should be populated with an individual User's first, last and middle names as registered on official government documentation e.g. Passport, Drivers Licence.
2.2	Other known name(s)	Provide any other names on record for a User e.g. where a User keeps their maiden name.	Optional	User	Free text field	This field should be populated with any additional official known names e.g. maiden name.

2.3	Personal email address	A personal email address is used to associate one individual with one SOURSD account, regardless of changes in employment. Personal email address also used for password recovery.	Mandatory	User	Free text field	This field should be populated with an individual User's personal email address to ensure a User's SOURSD identifier remains with them throughout their career. Example personal email accounts: Gmail account, Outlook Account, Yahoo account.
2.4	Terms and Conditions	The User understands conditions and guidelines for using the SOURSD tool including: acceptable behaviour, disclaimers, limitations of liability, termination provisions, applicable law.	Mandatory	User	Checkbox	

2.5	Location	To comply with Data Custodian information governance and information security requirements.	Mandatory	User	Select country from dropdown options	This field should be populated with the country an individual User's is accessing data from.
2.6	Identification Document Validation Technology (IDVT)	Validation of official government documentation – Driver's Licence or Passport. Validation of liveness/likeness identity verification – 'Selfie'. The data is not persistently stored	Optional	User	Uploaded to an independent verification service: Veriff	User is directed to the Veriff platform through the SOURSD tool. User takes a photo of their Passport or Driver's Licence, alongside their 'Selfie' using the Veriff platform. Document validation decision provided to SOURSD via Veriff automated feed.

User Profile: Affiliation Information

ID	Data field description	Why is this field captured?	Mandatory / Optional field	Populated by (owner)	Format field is populated	How field is populated
----	------------------------	-----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------	---------------------------	------------------------

DRAFT

2.7	<p>For each current employment or enrollment with an Organisation</p> <p>Organisation name</p>	<p>Associate an individual User with a Organisation. User provides organisation or institute name for each employment or enrollment with a Organisation.</p>	Mandatory	User	<p>Dropdown with Organisations autopopulated</p> <p>Free text field and link for User to request their Organisation register for a SOURSD account (this needs to include the name of the Organisation and an email address of a person in the Organisation requested to set up the account)</p>	<p>A User can add multiple current affiliations. This field should be populated with the Organisation a User is currently employed by (employees, individuals on an honorary contract) or an institute they are enrolled in (students).</p> <p>If an Organisation has a SOURSD account, a User can select their Organisation from the dropdown options and their Organisation will be autopopulated in this field.</p> <p>If an Organisation does not have a SOURSD account, a User can populate the free text field with the name of the Organisation and a email address field for the relevant</p>
-----	---	--	-----------	------	---	--

						contact requested to set up the account. The User should request their Organisation to register for a SOURSD account.
2.8	<p>For each current employment or enrollment with a Organisation</p> <p>Relationship with Organisation</p>	Establish if a User is substantively employed by an Organisation, on an honorary contract, or a student.	Mandatory	User	<p>Dropdown options:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee • Honorary contract • Student 	This field should be populated with a User's relationship with an Organisation.

2.9	<p>For each current employment or enrollment with a Organisation</p> <p>Staff ID/Student ID</p>	Associate an individual User with a Organisation. User provides staff ID/student ID for each Organisation they are employed by or enrolled in.	Mandatory (could fill in NA if needed)	User	Free text field	Dependent on the option selected above – employee, honorary contract, student – a User should populate this field with their staff/student ID, where available.
-----	--	--	--	------	-----------------	--

User Profile: Experience Information

ID	Data field description	Why is this field captured?	Mandatory / Optional field	Populated by (owner)	Format field is populated	How field is populated
2.10	ORCID	Existing persistent digital identifier providing information on employment history and publication record, for Users with an ORCID/where ORCID information is sufficiently populated.	Optional	User	Free text field	This field should be populated by researchers with existing ORCIDs or ORCIDs that are sufficiently populated.

2.11	CV	Upload of up-to-date CV to provide Data Custodians with information on a User's experience and professional employment.	Optional	User	Document upload	<p>CV file type should be in Word format. The maximum file size is 10MB.</p> <p>If ORCID field is sufficiently populated, a User does not have to upload a CV in addition to the ORCID field as information related to a User's employment history and publication record is included in a User's ORCID profile.</p>
------	----	---	----------	------	-----------------	--

2.12	A UK Statistics Authority Accredited Researcher appearing within the public registry	Provide Data Custodians with information on a User's accredited researcher status.	Optional	User	Checkbox	Is a criteria of the UKSA Digital Economy Act Research Code of Practice and Accreditation Criteria , a User must agree to their inclusion on a public record when undertaking research using data provided by an Digital Economy Act accredited processor (TRE/SDE).
------	--	--	----------	------	----------	--

2.13	Signed user declaration for DEA accredited environments	Provide Data Custodians with confidence a User has understood their responsibilities when accessing data from a specific TRE/SDE.	Optional	User	Checkbox	It is a criteria of the UKSA Digital Economy Act Research Code of Practice and Accreditation Criteria , that a DEA accredited User must "sign a declaration confirming that they have understood their responsibilities and will abide by the conditions imposed upon them, including protecting the confidentiality of information they access under the legislation".
------	---	---	----------	------	----------	---

User Profile: Training and Accreditation Information

ID	Data field description	Why is this field captured?	Mandatory / Optional field	Populated by (owner)	Format field is populated	How field is populated
----	------------------------	-----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------	---------------------------	------------------------

2.14	<p>For each completed training course</p> <p>Name of training course</p>	<p>Replace existing time-consuming manual processes where each Data Custodian contacts training providers and check internal records to establish if a User has completed mandatory training</p>	Mandatory	User	Free text field	<p>Example training courses include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ONS Safe Researcher Training (SRT) • TRE/SDE local training courses • MRC GDPR and Confidentiality training • Other training certificates related to the Safe People principle
2.15	<p>For each completed training course</p> <p>Date of issue and date of expiry</p>		Optional / Mandatory for SDE	User	Date selection	<p>Date selection from calander: date of issue, date of expiry.</p>

2.16	<p>For each completed training course</p> <p>Certification upload e.g.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ONS Safe Researcher Training (SRT) certification • Confirmation of local TRE/SDE training completion 		Optional	User	Document upload	<p>Training certification document type should be in Word or PDF format. The maximum file size is 10MB.</p>
2.17	<p>For each professional registration</p> <p>Professional registration name</p>		Mandatory	User	Free text field with option to add one or more professional registrations	<p>Examples of professional registrations include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UK Statistics Authority (UKSA)

2.18	<p>For each professional registration</p> <p>Professional registration ID</p>	Provide up-to-date professional registration information to Data Custodians.	Mandatory	User	Free text field	<p>Accredited Researcher (AR)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General Medical Council (GMC) • Nursing and Midwifery Council (NMC) • Health and Care Allied Professional Council (HCPC)
------	--	--	-----------	------	-----------------	--

Project Registry – Data Use Register variables

ID	Data field description	Why is this field captured?	Mandatory / Optional field	Populated by (owner)	Format field is populated	How field is populated
----	------------------------	-----------------------------	----------------------------	----------------------	---------------------------	------------------------

Data Use Register (DUR) Standard¹ **Safe People** variables

DRAFT

¹ Improving transparency in the use of health data for research: Recommendations for a data use register standard: <https://zenodo.org/records/5902743>

3.1	Lead applicant organisation name	The name of the legal entity that signs the contract to access the data.	Mandatory/ Recommended DUR <i>minimum</i> standard	Data Custodian	Automated or manual data feed from a Trusted Research Environment / NHS Secure Data Environment database to SOURSD. Data feed from SOURSD to the Health Data Research Gateway (if consent provided).	.
-----	----------------------------------	--	---	----------------	--	---

DRAFT

3.2	Fundors/Sponsors	The name of any funders or sponsors involved in the project.	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Organisation Delegate	Automated or manual data feed from a Trusted Research Environment / NHS Secure Data Environment database to SOURSD. Data feed from SOURSD to the Health Data Research Gateway (if consent provided).	
-----	------------------	--	---	-----------------------	--	--

DRAFT

3.3	Sub licence agreements	Identifies whether there are any permissions for the applicant to share the data beyond the named parties. e.g., NHS Digital may approve a data release to the ONS, who then makes decisions about access to accredited researchers undertaking approved projects in their own trusted research environment.	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Organisation Delegate	Automated or manual data feed from a Trusted Research Environment / NHS Secure Data Environment database to SOURSD. Data feed from SOURSD to the Health Data Research Gateway (if consent provided).	
Data Use Register (DUR) Standard Safe Project variables						
3.4	Project name	The name or title of the project/research study/request that the applicant is investigating through the use of health data.	Mandatory/ Recommended DUR <i>minimim</i> standard	Data Custodian		

3.5	Lay summary	A concise and clear description of the project, (e.g., as required by URKI in funding applications). It should outline the problem objectives and expected outcomes in language that is understandable to the general public. Applicants should be encouraged to limit this description.	Mandatory/ Recommended DUR <i>minimum</i> standard	Data Custodian	Automated or manual data feed from a Trusted Research Environment / NHS Secure Data Environment database to SOURSD. Data feed from SOURSD to the Health Data Research Gateway (if consent provided).
3.6	Public benefit statement	A description in plain English of the anticipated outcomes, or impact of project on the general public.	Mandatory/ Recommended DUR <i>minimum</i> standard	Data Custodian	
3.7	Latest approval date	The last date the data access request for this project was approved by a data custodian.	Optional/ Recommended DUR <i>minimum</i> standard	Data Custodian	

3.8	Project ID	A unique identifier for the project that is preferably an industry used	Mandatory	Data Custodian		
3.9	Request category type	This categorises the 'purpose of the share' (i.e., research, policy development, etc).	Mandatory	Data Custodian		
3.10	Technical summary	A summary of the proposed research, in a manner that is suitable for a specialist reader.	Mandatory	Data Custodian		
3.11	Other approval committees	Reference to other decision-making bodies that the project has already been authorised by.	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian		
3.12	Project start date	The date the project is scheduled to start or actual start date.	Mandatory	Data Custodian		
3.13	Project end date	The date the project is scheduled to finish or actual end date.	Mandatory	Data Custodian		

Data Use Register (DUR) Standard Safe Data variables						
3.14	Dataset(s) name	The name of the dataset(s) being accessed.	Optional/ Recommended DUR <i>minimum</i> standard	Data Custodian	Automated or manual data feed from a Trusted Research Environment / NHS Secure Data	
3.15	Data sensitivity level	The level of identifiability of the data being accessed, as defined by Understanding Patient Data.	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian	Environment database to SOURSD. Data feed from SOURSD to the Health Data Research Gateway (if consent provided).	
3.16	Legal basis for provision of data under Article 6	The lawful basis for processing is set out in Article 6 of the GDPR. At least one legal basis must apply whenever you process personal data. Processing shall be lawful only if and to the extent that at least one of the following applies.	Mandatory	Data Custodian		

3.17	Lawful conditions for provision of data under Article 9	Processing of personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership, and the processing of genetic data, biometric data for the purpose of uniquely identifying a natural person, data concerning health or data concerning a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian		
------	---	---	---	----------------	--	--

3.18	Common Law Duty of Confidentiality	<p>If confidential information is being disclosed, the organisations holding this data (both the organisation disclosing the information and the recipient organisation) must also have a lawful basis to hold and use this information, and if applicable, have a condition to hold and use special categories of confidential information, and be fair and transparent about how they hold and use this data.</p> <p><i>This does not apply if one of the following applies.</i></p>	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian		<p>In England and Wales, if you are using section 251 of the NHS Act 2006 (s251) as a legal basis for identifiable data, you will need to ensure that you have the latest approval letter and application.</p> <p>For Scotland this application will be reviewed by the Public Benefit and Privacy Panel.</p> <p>In Northern Ireland it will be considered by the Privacy Advisory Committee. If you are using patient consent as the legal basis, you will need to provide all relevant consent forms and information leaflets.</p>
------	------------------------------------	--	---	----------------	--	--

3.19	National data opt- out applied?	Specifies whether the preference for people to opt-out of their confidential patient information being used for secondary use has been applied to the data prior to release.	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian		
3.20	Request frequency	Determines whether this is a 'one-off' request or a recurring dataset to be provided over a specific time period	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian		

3.21	For linked datasets, specify how the linkage will take place	Specifies whether applicant intends for the datasets to be linked with any additional datasets. Relevant information on the organisations undertaking linkages and how the linkage will take place must also be disclosed. As well as a summary of the risks/mitigations to be considered	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian		
3.22	Approach to data minimisation	Outline the measures taken to minimise the data in line with GDPR.	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian		
3.23	Description of the confidential data being used	A description of the specific patient identifiable fields that have been included in the dataset(s) being accessed.	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian		

3.24	Release/Access date	The date the data access was granted and active research started.	Optional/ Recommended as part of DUR <i>full specification</i>	Data Custodian		
Data Use Register (DUR) Standard Safe Setting variables						
3.25	Access type	Determines whether the data will be accessed within a Trusted Research Environment (TRE) or via a data release model.	Mandatory/ Recommended DUR minimim standard	Data Custodian	Automated or manual data feed from a Trusted Research Environment / NHS Secure Data Environment database to SOURSD. Data feed from SOURSD to the Health Data Research Gateway (if consent provided).	
3.26	How has data been processed to enhance privacy?	Description of the tools or software used to reduce level of identifiable data being shared.	Optional/Recomm ended as part of DUR full specification	Data Custodian		
Data Use Register (DUR) Standard Safe Outputs variables						

3.27	Link to research outputs	A URL link to any academic or non-academic research outputs, as they become available, including code used.	Optional/Recommended as part of DUR full specification	Data Custodian	Automated or manual data feed from a Trusted Research Environment / NHS Secure Data	
3.28	New data assets created	Specifies the procedures and systems in place for the secure management, storage and archiving of data assets created as a result of linkage.	Optional/Recommended as part of DUR full specification	Data Custodian	Environment database to SOURSD. Data feed from SOURSD to the Health Data Research Gateway (if consent provided).	

Project Registry – Approved Users and Organisations

3.29	Approved Users and Organisations	Provide Data Custodians with information on which Users and Organisations are currently approved to access a TRE/SDE, on a per-Project basis.	Mandatory	Data Custodians	Automated or manual data feed to SOURSD from individual TRE/SDE databases	
------	----------------------------------	---	-----------	-----------------	---	--

3.30	Users and Organisations Pending Approval	Data Custodians to provide information on which Users and Organisations are awaiting approval to access a TRE/SDE, on a per-Project basis.	Mandatory	Data Custodians	<p>Status of application field:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • User approved • Organisation approved • User pending approval • Organisation pending approval • User not approved • Organisation not approved 	
------	--	--	-----------	-----------------	--	--

Configurable rules for Data Custodians

SOURSD will not make decisions on behalf of TREs/SDEs, the decision on whether or not to approve a User or Organisation still remains with TREs/SDEs. However, SOURSD will contain a rules engine to allow TREs/SDEs to **build automated decision models and be alerted in real-time, when specific data fields do not comply with rules** set by the TRE/SDE. TREs/SDEs can view data populated within SOURSD associated with a User or Organisation to decide as to whether data fields comply with relevant TRE/SDEs policies or procedures.

This functionality can be utilised at the point of “verifying” a User or Organisation and will also flag when data recorded regarding a User or Organisation changes and breaches a rule, after initial verification e.g. a Users’ training certification expires or a User leaves an Organisation. The configurable rules defined in this standard are informed by consultation with IG experts and independent legal guidance, and rules are fully customisable for specific TREs/SDEs.

Here we propose a list of rules, which TREs/SDEs can chose to configure (or not) within the SOURSD tool to flag potential issues with the “safeness” of a User or Organisation.

The configurable rules differ depending on:

- if data held by a TRE/SDE **IS** considered to be anonymised in the hands of the User
- if data held by a TRE/SDE **is NOT** considered to be anonymised in the hands of the User

SOURSD can flag breaches to rules at the time a User or Organisation is being reviewed at project approval stage, and also automatically let a TRE/SDE know if a breach of a rule happens during the course of an on-going project because a field is updated.

Condition	Rule	Minimum dataset data field reference	Guidance
If data held by a TRE/SDE is NOT considered to be anonymised in the hands of the User	A User should be located in a country which adheres to equivalent data protection laws (SOURSD could flag if a User location is not within a defined list of countries with adequate protection)	2.5 User Location	Users to populate location within SOURSD profile. User location should be in a country that is within the EEA or has adequacy status due to data sharing and data transfer requirements – see European Commission² guidance for countries providing adequate protection.
if data held by a TRE/SDE IS considered to be anonymised in the hands of the User – All projects	Additional organisation due diligence checks should be carried out on Organisations who are not approved Organisations.	1.6 Organisation Name 1.7 Organisation address 1.9 Organisation Companies House filing	Organisation due diligence check either through a self-assessment against local TRE/SDE standards or potentially using a SaaS organisation due diligence solution.

² European Commission: Adequacy decisions: https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/international-dimension-data-protection/adequacy-decisions_en

	<p>(SOURSD could be configured to flag organisations not on lists of registered research organisations)</p>		
	<p>A user must have completed mandatory TRE/SDE training before accessing a TRE/SDE.</p> <p>(SOURSD could flag if a user has not completed mandatory training courses required by the specific SDE/TRE)</p>	<p>2.16 Training course name 2.17 Training course date of issue and expiry 2.18 Training course certification upload</p>	<p>Local TRE/SDE training includes User completion of training video or assessment associated with access to de-identified patient-level data.</p>
	<p>A user needs to have agreed to the Terms of Use for a specific TRE/SDE.</p> <p>(SOURSD could flag if a user has not agreed to Terms of Use)</p>	<p>(new fields to be added)</p>	<p>Terms of Use specifically for a User to accept SOURSD terms of user as opposed to TRE/SDE specific terms of use.</p>

	<p>An organisation must have provided data security compliance accreditation information.</p> <p>(SOURSD could flag if a host organisation has required data security certifications)</p>	<p>1.21 Data security compliance checkbox selection</p> <p>1.21 Data security compliance ID</p>	<p>Data Custodian data security accreditation requirements include one or more of the following: Cyber Essentials, Cyber Essentials Plus, ISO27001, DSPT.</p>
	<p>An Organisation must have at least one delegate to vouch for a User's behaviour within a TRE/SDE</p> <p>(SOURSD could flag if a host organisation has added delegate information to their SOURSD profile)</p>	<p>1.17 Delegate department</p> <p>1.18 Delegate name</p> <p>1.19 Delegate email address</p> <p>1.20 Delegate job title</p>	<p>Organisation delegates are nominated administrative groups or individuals within organisation departments that confirm a User's identity and affiliation.</p> <p>Organisation delegate is accountable for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verifying affiliation with a User • Accepting SOURSD terms of use • Verifying information populated within SOURSD is accurate and authorised on behalf of the organisation

Appendix

Appendix 1: SOURSD Project overview

The challenge

[Trusted Research Environments](#) (TREs), also known as Data Safe Havens or Secure Data Environments (SDEs), have a legal responsibility to maintain the privacy and integrity of sensitive data. TREs/SDEs need to establish:

Whether each **User**/researcher requesting access to data:

- is trained in handling sensitive data;
- is who they say they are;

- does not have any other employments which might have an impact on their classification of “safe”.

That the **Organisation** the researcher is affiliated with – through an employment contract, honorary contract, or as a student – for the purposes of the research proposed to be conducted:

- takes full responsibility for the actions of the researcher;
- is aware of their legal responsibilities and will carry out appropriate actions if the researcher is found to break any of the data access agreement clauses;
- is an appropriate Organisation with legitimate reasons for carrying out research in the public interest;
- is responsible for ensuring the researcher has been suitably trained in accessing sensitive data.

Currently, these checks are highly manual and time-consuming and are duplicated within each different TRE/SDE for each research Project – putting extra administrative burden on researchers, TREs/SDEs and Organisations. There are no standardised mechanisms for TREs/SDEs to communicate researcher expertise or identity with other TREs/SDEs, and Organisations also do not have an easy way to track which of their employees are working on which sensitive data Projects in which TRE/SDE.

The solution

The Safe Organisation and User Registry for Sensitive Data (SOURSD) project – previously named the Researcher Registry Project – is one of the [four pilot Projects funded by UKRI](#) which aims to simplify decision-making processes when granting researchers access to sensitive health and administrative data. In line with the [Five Safes Framework](#) ‘Safe People’ principle, SOURSD aims to provide consistency across Organisations, along with confidence in the accuracy of the data populated within the tool, to reduce the burden for both TREs/SDEs and researchers, enabling simpler, faster, more reliable decision-making.

The SOURSD Minimum Viable Product (MVP) will launch in beta at the end of March 2025 enabling the following capabilities for Data Custodians, Users and Organisations:

- **Streamline the process to request data access** and minimise a significant bottleneck currently experienced by researchers attempting to use sensitive data.

- **Enable decision making by providing a centralised ‘Know Your User and Organisation’ system** for researchers and Organisations to share relevant information and for TREs to assess if a person is "safe".
- **Support federated TRE networks** by providing visibility across TREs including recording approvals for previous Projects carried out with TREs.
- **Enable account linkage or creation** by enabling Single Sign-On (SSO) through multiple providers through OICD Keycloak, enabling Users to associate their SOURSD account with other accounts e.g. Health Data Research Gateway User account.
- **Enable Organisations to view and track** which of their employees is working on which Project on which TRE/SDE across the UK in one place.
- **Provide an MPV technical solution** for the NHS Research SDE Network to use by the end of the Project, supporting TREs from other data domains to adopt over time.

SOURSD enables **Users** who wish to access sensitive data for research / development to populate a profile with information such as their identity, training record, experience, qualifications, and employments. Users can be “affiliated” by Organisations who employ them or teach them. User profiles are not publicly visible but are visible to verified Data Custodians across the UK. Data Custodians can view User profiles when they are assessing data access applications, supporting them to assess the “Safe People” component of the [Five Safes Framework](#). There are many types of Users, for example, researchers, data analysts and AI developers. Users can also come from many sectors including industry, academia and the public sector. If you are an individual who wishes to access sensitive data for research,

SOURSD enables **Organisations** who employ or teach individuals who access sensitive data for research to set up a profile including information such as their identity and data security compliance. Organisations can view the SOURSD profiles of Users that have requested that the Organisation “affiliates” them. Data Custodians can view Organisation profiles when they are assessing data access applications, supporting them to assess the “Safe People” component of the [Five Safes Framework](#). Organisations come from many sectors including industry, academia and the public sector. If you are representing an Organisation who employees or teaches Users who are accessing sensitive data for research

SOURSD enables **Data Custodians** to view User and Organisation profiles as part of their assessment the “Safe People” component of the [Five Safes Framework](#). SOURSD does not make decisions as to who is a “Safe Person” or a “Safe Organisation” but will provide information associated with Users and their Organisations and flag whether that information breaks any customisable rules set by the TRE/SDE.

SOURSD aims to provide the following key benefits for Data Custodians, Users, Organisations, and the public:

DRAFT

